



AQP11

AQP12

Metazoa III

Invertebrate unorthodox AQPs

Fungi

Amoebozoa

Evosea

MDC1

SAR

SAR VI

SAR VII

LIPS

Alveolata, Stramenopila

SIP-1

SIP-2

SIPs

SIP-1

SIP-2

SIPs